

Business applications of Artificial Intelligence

Construction sector
briefing paper

Innovate
UK

BridgeAI

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About the briefing paper series

A significant barrier to AI adoption in the business world is the scarcity of clear, accessible information on how to leverage AI to enhance organisational productivity. Understanding the practical applications of AI is a prerequisite for companies to identify relevant opportunities and develop a strategy to operationalise them. To address this need, the AI Governance and Regulatory Innovation team at The Alan Turing Institute is pursuing a research project to illuminate how businesses in the four BridgeAI priority sectors of agriculture, forestry and fishing, construction, creative industries, and transportation and storage can leverage AI to be more productive.

The first milestone of this project is the publication of a framework for categorising and analysing business applications of AI and a brief analysis of sector-specific AI use cases. Our findings are published as a **series of five documents**: four sector-specific briefings complemented by a paper presenting a framework to categorise and analyse AI use cases. The sector briefings offer a short analysis of the high-level economic features of each

sector in the UK, the specific challenges to AI adoption faced by businesses in that sector, and five business applications of AI per sector. Each sector brief can be read as a standalone document. The paper on the classification framework presents the tool that we developed to categorise and analyse AI use cases in a business context. In addition to providing the hermeneutical structure underpinning our research, this tool provides a valuable resource for businesses trying to identify relevant AI opportunities. Companies can use this framework as a starting point to build on and develop their bespoke methodology to identify, select, and implement the right AI solutions.

The second milestone of this project will be to refine the framework based on feedback collected after the publication of this first exploratory version and expand its scope to include information about the risks connected to each AI use case and the mitigation strategies that can be adopted to address those risks in that specific context.

Desired impact

Our research aims to support businesses at the early stages of their AI adoption cycle. By providing a conceptual framework to systematically categorise business applications of AI and offering concrete examples of sector-specific AI applications, we hope to help businesses identify possible uses of AI in their area, understand the nature of relevant technological solutions, and develop a sound strategy to operationalise those solutions responsibly.

Intended audience

The audience for this briefing series is primarily businesses within the BridgeAI priority sectors looking to adopt AI to support their operations. It is worth noting that the accompanying framework was developed based on generalised principles which are applicable to any sector and should, therefore, provide value to a wider audience, including non-commercial organisations. In addition to benefiting companies, this briefing series provides valuable resources for government officials and regulators aiming to understand how businesses use AI, as well as for training officers and advisors seeking a systematic approach to developing AI strategies for business.

AI Governance and Regulatory Innovation team

This work has been completed by researchers from The Alan Turing Institute who are part of the AI Governance and Regulatory Innovation team based within the Public Policy programme. As part of our offering for the BridgeAI programme, we support UK businesses navigate the increasingly complex AI governance landscape. This is delivered through training and sector-specific research on some of the most pressing AI governance issues, as well as by engaging with regional AI policy stakeholders to help consolidate a nationwide community of actors invested in responsible AI governance.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming the global economy, yet many sectors of the business world are only beginning to explore the opportunities AI technologies offer. Despite AI adoption being on the rise globally, the technology's potential to support organisations by improving their productivity and competitiveness remains partially unexplored in many economic areas. For instance, only 20% of small companies in the UK say they use at least one AI tool as part of their operations, despite 55% stating that AI could provide benefits to their business.¹ To ensure AI will benefit a wide range of sectors and regions and support businesses in their AI adoption journey, the UK government launched several high-impact initiatives to “invest and plan for the long-term needs of the [country's] AI ecosystem”.² These include, among others, the BridgeAI programme, which aims to foster the development and adoption of AI technologies in sectors with high potential for AI-driven economic transformation.³

Despite important steps forward, several barriers to widespread AI adoption still exist. These include the high cost of AI solutions, the uncertainty of their return on investment,⁴ the scarcity of relevant technical and business skills in the labour market,⁵ regulatory uncertainty

related to the development and use of AI,⁶ low rates of senior management buy-in, the difficulty of collecting or accessing high-quality data,⁷ and scepticism for some AI applications caused by ethical concerns around issues such as bias and privacy. At a more fundamental level, many companies struggle to identify the right AI opportunities due to a general lack of awareness about the full range of practical business applications of these technologies. In other words, many companies are unsure about how exactly to leverage the potential of AI to support their business goals. For instance, a recent survey of 100 business leaders from different countries and sectors found that while “leaders are overwhelmingly looking at AI as an opportunity, the picture is not yet clear on how to harness this opportunity practically.”⁸

One way to address this uncertainty is disseminating knowledge about existing AI use cases and best practices in the industry. Understanding how other companies use AI technologies, be it to support internal functions or to build better products and services, enables businesses that are considering embarking on the journey of AI adoption to think creatively about how AI can add value to their organisation.

1 Russell, C. & E. Quist (2024). *Redefining intelligence: The growth of AI among small businesses*. Federation of Small Businesses. <https://www.fsb.org.uk/resource-report/redefining-intelligence.html>.

2 UK Government (2021). *National AI Strategy*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-ai-strategy/national-ai-strategy-html-version>.

3 Innovate UK (2023). *BridgeAI*. <https://iuk.ktn-uk.org/programme/bridgeai/>.

4 CDEI (2021). *UK Business Innovation Survey*. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/61bb2e77e90e07044462d8b7/Business_Innovation_Survey_2021.pdf.

5 *AI ecosystem survey informing the National AI Strategy*. The Alan Turing Institute, https://www.turing.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2021-09/ai-strategy-survey_results_020921.pdf.

6 Gillespie, N., S. Lockey, C. Curtis, et al. (2023). *Trust in Artificial Intelligence: A global study*. The University of Queensland and KPMG Australia. https://policy-futures.centre.uq.edu.au/files/16650/Trust%20in%20AI%20Global%20Report_2023_UQ.pdf.

7 Mittal, N., Saif, I. & Ammanath, B. (2022). *Fueling the AI transformation: Four key actions powering widespread value from AI, right now*. Deloitte, <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/us/Documents/deloitte-analytics/us-ai-institute-state-of-ai-fifth-edition.pdf>.

8 Bicakci, B. et al. (2024). *Leadership in the Age of AI*. EgonZehnder and Kearney. <https://www.egonzehnder.com/leadership-in-the-age-of-ai>.

Building on this premise, this briefing aims to contribute to demystifying how businesses in the construction sector can use AI to be more competitive, sustainable, and productive. The first part of the briefing offers an overview of the key economic features of the UK's construction sector, including a brief discussion of sector-specific challenges to AI adoption. In the second part, we leverage the **AI use case classification framework** to discuss five sectoral AI applications. Each AI use case is accompanied by a use case card, which provides a visual summary of the key information related to that application. These examples illustrate the wide-ranging and diverse potential applications of AI in the construction sector.

Sector overview and challenges to AI adoption

Construction is a diverse sector that includes activities ranging from the construction and maintenance of infrastructure and buildings to the manufacture and supply of construction products.⁹ The construction sector is one of the largest industries in the UK. It employs 9% of the UK workforce and contributes circa 7% of the country's GDP.¹⁰ Approximately 60% of construction output is new build, whilst 40% is repair and maintenance.¹¹ Over the last decade, the sector's productivity grew by roughly 1% per year, confirming it as a stable pillar of the UK economy while also raising questions about how to improve its efficiency.¹² Considering the sector's relatively slow productivity growth, the promise of new technologies like AI to unlock new capabilities, streamline processes, and cut production costs are especially attractive to the construction sector.¹³ Some of the domains where the application of AI in construction is especially promising include logistics, supply chain management, project planning, design, worksite safety, and the reduction of carbon emissions.

Despite the value AI could add to the construction sector, realising AI's potential faces several adoption challenges. Specific blockers vary depending on the sub-sector, the project's size, the technologies used for a project, and the types of firms adopting the technology. Nevertheless, it is possible to identify some overarching, high-level challenges that are common across the sector. These include structural features of the sector, like the high-stakes safety risks associated with manual work and the complexity of construction projects, as well as AI-specific challenges, including the dynamic nature of construction sites, the lack of platforms to effectively share data, the fact that data produced within specific projects are often lost once projects are completed, regulatory uncertainty on the use of AI and connected compliance concerns, the lack of technical AI skills, and uncertainty around the concrete benefits of specific AI use cases.¹⁴

9 Designing Buildings (2022). *UK construction industry*. https://www.designingbuildings.co.uk/wiki/UK_construction_industry

10 Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors (2022). *RICS calls for industry and government to futureproof UK construction*. <https://www.rics.org/news-insights/rics-calls-for-industry-and-government-to-futureproof-uk-construction#:~:text=Construction%20is%20critical%20to%20the,continued%20growth%2C%20headwinds%20are%20growing>.

11 Designing Buildings (2022). *UK Construction Industry*. https://www.designingbuildings.co.uk/wiki/UK_construction_industry.

12 Regona, M. et al. (2022). Opportunities and Adoption Challenges of AI in the Construction Industry: A PRISMA Review. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc8010045>.

13 Cabinet Office (2011). *Government Construction Strategy*. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/61152/Government-Construction-Strategy_0.pdf

14 Regona et al. (2022). cit.

Sector structure

The construction sector covers a wide range of different activities. From the construction of factories and power plants to highways and roads, commercial buildings, and housing, construction companies can specialise in a variety of domains. While it is important to consider that some construction companies can operate across two or more sub-sectors, it is still possible to identify segments of the sector that engage in qualitatively different types of construction work. For the purposes of this research, we propose a simplified version of the UK Standard Industrial Classification sub-sector categorisation.¹⁵ More specifically, we refer to the following construction sub-sectors:

- Buildings
- Civil engineering
- Specialised construction works

Businesses operating in the 'Buildings' sub-sector include those developing projects for the construction of and constructing buildings for residential and commercial use. These can be publicly or privately owned, and include, among others, houses, offices, shops, factories, warehouses, agricultural buildings, schools, universities, public care homes, and hospitals. The 'Civil engineering' sub-sector includes businesses constructing infrastructure such as roads and motorways, railways, bridges and tunnels, utility projects for fluids, utility projects for electricity and telecommunications, and water projects. The 'Specialised construction works' sub-sector is comprised of businesses specialised in work that is complementary to the construction, or preparation for construction, of buildings and civil engineering projects. These include businesses specialised in repair and maintenance, demolition, site preparation, plumbing, plastering, roofing, scaffolding erection, floor and wall covering, and other specialised activities. All three sub-sectors encompass companies specialising in construction-related services and product manufacturing.

¹⁵ Office for National Statistics (2007). *UK SIC 2007*. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/methodology/classificationsandstandards/ukstandardindustrialclassificationofeconomicactivities/uksic2007>.

AI applications for the construction sector

AI applications are increasingly common in the construction sector, with a growing number of use cases based on generative AI, machine vision, and simulation technologies. Examples include monitoring construction worksites, predictive machinery maintenance, and project site modelling. These use cases offer insights into AI's potential to benefit the sector while also highlighting some of the challenges related to its development and adoption. Below is a description of five construction use cases that we analysed using the framework presented in **this accompanying paper**.

Real-time worksite safety monitoring

Worksite hazards are a major concern in the construction sector. They put workers' lives at risk and can cause costly disruptions. AI technologies can support in detecting these hazards before they escalate, helping safeguard worker safety and minimise losses. For example, AI technologies can be used for real-time worksite monitoring. By processing visual data from cameras placed around the worksite, an AI system can identify and flag instances of unsafe behaviour and other safety hazards. The results of the analysis can then be used to inform the company's worksite safety policies as well as future training and education programmes. This AI solution can

be applied to different kinds of worksites and is relevant for all construction sub-sectors. It has the potential to support productivity by reducing worksite incidents and minimising compliance costs for the company deploying it. Similar AI solutions process data containing, among other things, images of workers. For this reason, the companies deploying them should adopt adequate personal data protection measures, such as blurring or masking people's faces before processing the data. Companies deploying these systems should consider possible risks related to the workplace surveillance capabilities of such AI systems and adopt relevant internal policies to address them.

Business challenge:

Improve workplace safety in construction sites.

Solution:

Construction worksites are monitored by cameras and an AI system uses that data to detect and flag instances of unsafe behaviour, helping to inform safety policies and training.

Organisation

Type of use case

Process-centric

Business function

Compliance and justice

Data

Type of input data

Visual

Processing of personal data

Yes

AI system

AI system capabilities

Recognition and detection, Recommendation

Environment

Virtual

Readiness level

Operational

Economic sector

Sector

Construction

Sub-sector

Buildings, Civil engineering, Specialised construction works

Automated construction schedule management

Construction and infrastructure projects can be complex endeavours involving multiple stages of development and requiring various resources. To maximise efficient delivery and minimise time and cost, it is important to design project schedules that avoid delays and optimise the use of resources. Companies can use AI to automate parts of their construction schedule management processes. More specifically, AI-enabled techniques can be used to simulate, analyse, and compare scheduling options, including cost, time, various methods of execution, and workforce density to then recommend a resource-efficient project schedule.

Business challenge:

Optimise resource allocation in construction project plans.

Solution:

An AI system simulates, analyses, and compares alternative scheduling options to recommend a resource-efficient schedule for a construction project.

Organisation

Type of use case

Process-centric

Business function

Planning and budgeting

Data

Type of input data

Numerical, Text

Processing of personal data

No

AI system

AI system capabilities

Optimisation, Simulation

Environment

Virtual

Readiness level

Operational

Economic sector

Sector

Construction

Sub-sector

Buildings, Civil engineering, Specialised construction works

Process control optimisation for cement plants

The construction sector is a major contributor to global CO2 emissions and faces pressure to reduce its environmental impact. AI technologies can help construction companies meet their sustainability targets and reduce inefficiencies. AI technologies can be used to develop highly realistic 'digital twins' of complex systems – such as industrial plants – with the goal of monitoring and optimising them. By analysing real-time data collected by distributed control systems, digital twins deliver accurate, real-time representations of the functioning of specific components of the system. For example, an AI system trained on the

simulated model of a cement plant can provide insights into how to optimise the plant's pyro-processes by analysing the thermodynamic properties of the plant's kilns, identifying energy inefficiencies, and suggesting options to reduce fuel consumption to specialised operators.

Business challenge:

Reduce the costs and environmental impact of pyroprocesses in cement plants.

Solution:

An AI system creates a dynamic digital replica of a cement plant to test different combinations of complex processes, helping to find ways to reduce fuel consumption.

Organisation

Type of use case

Process-centric

Business function

Production,
Compliance and justice

Data

Type of input data

Numerical, Signal

Processing of personal data

No

AI system

AI system capabilities

Optimisation,
Simulation

Environment

Virtual

Readiness level

Operational

Economic sector

Sector

Construction

Sub-sector

Civil engineering

Predictive maintenance of construction machinery

Better maintenance processes can reduce the likelihood of accidents caused by malfunctioning equipment, leading to the creation of a safer work environment and increased operational efficiency. Traditional machinery maintenance often relies on scheduled inspections or reactive measures when a failure occurs. AI technologies can support businesses in making internal maintenance functions more efficient by cutting costs and improving the durability of machinery. Companies can leverage machine learning algorithms to analyse

machinery data and predict potential issues before they result in downtime. AI systems for predictive maintenance can be relevant for companies across the whole construction sector. Typically, AI-enabled solutions for predictive maintenance are based on the analysis of numerical data about the past performance of a machine as well as dynamic data collected through IoT sensors and other types of physical measurement equipment. Based on such data, the AI system can provide information about when the machine will likely require maintenance.

Business challenge:

Reduce accidents caused by malfunctioning equipment and increase operational efficiency.

Solution:

An AI system analyses data about a machine's past performance as well as data collected through sensors and physical equipment to suggest when the machine will need maintenance.

Organisation

Type of use case

Process-centric

Business function

Management of organisational assets

Data

Type of input data

Numerical, Signal

Processing of personal data

No

AI system

AI system capabilities

Prediction and forecasting

Environment

Virtual

Readiness level

Operational

Economic sector

Sector

Construction

Sub-sector

Buildings, Civil engineering, Specialised construction works

Automated reality capture for project site modelling

Managing complex construction projects remotely poses significant logistical challenges for construction companies needing to undertake monitoring and quality assurance throughout a project. Digital modelling of physical spaces is already an established solution to these challenges. Building on more traditional solutions for digital modelling, AI can support modelling by automating reality capture processes, speeding up development processes and generating more dynamic models. For example, an AI system can process visual data captured by a 360° camera mounted on the

helmet of a project officer walking around the space. This operation can be repeated regularly to create a dynamic model of that space. The model enables surveyors to explore the space virtually, plan future work, and monitor changes to the space. Considering the type of data processed by the AI system and the data collection process, it is reasonable to assume that images of staff and contractors could be captured and processed by the AI system. As such, measures such as blurring the faces of affected individuals before processing the data should be taken to address legal and ethical issues regarding personal data protection.

Business challenge:

Enable remote construction site monitoring and quality assurance.

Solution:

An AI system creates a digital model of a project site based on images captured by a 360° camera mounted on the helmet of a person walking around the site. This operation can be repeated regularly to create a dynamic model of that space. The model allows operators to explore the space virtually, plan future work, and monitor changes to the space.

Organisation

Type of use case

Process-centric

Business function

Production

Data

Type of input data

Visual

Processing of personal data

Yes

AI system

AI system capabilities

Recognition and detection, Simulation

Environment

Virtual

Readiness level

Operational

Economic sector

Sector

Construction

Sub-sector

Buildings, Specialised construction works

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